

Relationship between lifestyle, body composition, and psychological well-being in individuals with severe mental disorders: A comprehensive analysis

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ABSTRACT

Severe mental disorders (SMD) are associated with a reduced life expectancy, influenced by factors such as obesity, sedentary behavior, poor nutrition, and social challenges, including stigma. Individuals with SMD face significant deficiencies in physical, psychological, and social health, with implications for their overall quality of life and well-being. Although these dimensions have been explored separately, there are few studies that integrate these variables to understand their interactions and guide more effective interventions. In this study, bioimpedance measurements, validated physical tests, and psychometric scales were used on a sample of 311 individuals with SMD, aged 18–68 years, from the Andalusia region (Southern Spain). Physical variables (fat mass, visceral fat, lean mass), eating habits, physical activity levels, and psychological variables (mental well-being and quality of life) were assessed. The results revealed high levels of body and visceral fat, insufficient lean mass, unbalanced diets with high consumption of ultra-processed foods, low levels of physical activity, and reduced scores in mental well-being and quality of life. Notably, linear regression analyses showed that time spent on physical activity was the only significant predictor of mental well-being and quality of life, while other measured variables did not show a significant effect. This highlights the unique contribution of physical activity in improving psychological outcomes for individuals with SMD. These findings underscore the need for comprehensive programs that combine strategies to improve diet, physical activity, and psychological well-being, promoting sustainable and effective physical activity programs to enhance the quality of life of individuals with SMD.

Despite advancements in knowledge about mental health and psychological research, individuals with severe mental disorders (SMD) continue to face multiple barriers that affect both their quality of life and life expectancy. This population group includes schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, severe personality disorders, and severe forms of major depression. However, it is important to note that cases of severe depression were not included in this study, as the collaborating institution—the Andalusian Public Foundation for the Social Integration of

People with Mental Illness (FAISEM)—primarily serves individuals with psychotic disorders and severe personality disorders. FAISEM is a public foundation based in Andalusia (Southern Spain) that provides community-based services, residential programs, and social support to promote the inclusion and recovery of individuals with SMD. Individuals with SMD not only experience pronounced social and healthcare stigma but also suffers from a range of disadvantages associated with medical care and physical comorbidities. These challenges contribute to a life

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expectancy that is 15–20 years shorter than that of the general population (Laursen et al., 2014; Thornicroft, 2011). Paradoxically, this fact is not always reflected in the priority given to these individuals within healthcare systems, perpetuating avoidable inequalities (Lawrence et al., 2013).

The physical and psychological manifestations of SMD are multifaceted and deeply interconnected. Physically, individuals with SMD show a higher prevalence of cardiovascular diseases, metabolic syndrome, obesity and other health problems that compromise functional capacities (Correll et al., 2017; Vancampfort et al., 2015). Psychologically, they often experience social isolation, low self-esteem, anxiety, and depression, all of which significantly impact their quality of life (Nevarez-Flores et al., 2019; Berghöfer et al., 2020; Vaca and Martínez, 2019). These manifestations not only affect their physical and mental health but also limit their autonomy and daily functioning, creating a constant state of vulnerability.

These physical and psychological problems are exacerbated by specific lifestyle and environmental factors. In the physical domain, sedentary behavior is common among individuals with SMD and can be partly explained by reduced energy and motivation, which are common side effects of antipsychotic medications used in the treatment of certain conditions, such as schizophrenia (Vancampfort et al., 2016). Although physical activity has been shown to be an effective strategy for improving mental health, participation levels remain low due to barriers to motivation, social stigma, and limited access to appropriate programs (Ashdown-Franks et al., 2018; Stubbs et al., 2018; Méndez-Aguado et al., 2023; Romain et al., 2020). Additionally, individuals with SMD often experience a sense of isolation (Lien et al., 2018; Rezaie et al., 2017), which further exacerbates psychological distress.

Dietary habits also play a critical role. Individuals with SMD often consume diets high in refined carbohydrates and saturated fats, with low intake of fruits, vegetables, fiber, and essential nutrients (Aucoin et al., 2018; Martland et al., 2021). This unbalanced diet is associated with higher levels of visceral fat, obesity, and metabolic dysfunction (Lawrence and Baker, 2019; Janochova et al., 2019; Haberka et al., 2018). The consumption of ultra-processed foods is particularly concerning in this population. These products, classified under the NOVA system, include sugary beverages, processed snacks, refined cereals, and pre-cooked foods, all of which are associated with adverse effects on metabolic and cardiovascular health (Monteiro et al., 2017; Teasdale et al., 2019). Harmful habits such as smoking and excessive alcohol consumption are also widespread, further perpetuating comorbidities (Guckel et al., 2022; Stubbs et al., 2018).

These interconnected lifestyle factors not only worsen physical conditions but also have a profound impact on psychological well-being. Recent studies have indicated that individuals with SMD consistently exhibit lower levels of mental well-being and quality of life compared to the general population (Berghöfer et al., 2020; Vaca and Martínez, 2019). This decline is closely linked to a lack of social support, isolation, and economic difficulties, which perpetuate a cycle of physical and psychological deterioration (Nevarez-Flores et al., 2019).

Despite numerous studies addressing these variables in isolation, research integrating physical and psychological aspects in a comprehensive analysis remains scarce. This lack of a holistic approach limits our understanding of how these variables interact and how they can be effectively addressed in intervention programs.

Considering the above, this study aims to conduct a comprehensive evaluation of physical condition, body composition, physical activity levels, eating behaviors, and variables related to quality of life and well-being in individuals with SMD. It seeks to explore the interrelationships among these variables to identify patterns that can guide the design of more effective and personalized intervention programs. These programs should not only address the physical and psychological deficiencies identified but also consider the specific barriers and facilitators that affect this population. The joint analysis of these variables will advance a more comprehensive understanding of the needs and challenges faced

by individuals with SMD, facilitating the creation of intervention strategies that improve both their quality of life and overall well-being. This comprehensive approach is essential for addressing the multiple dimensions of SMD, promoting greater inclusion and equity in healthcare.

1. Method

1.1. Participants

The participants of this study included a total of 311 individuals with SMD (239 men; 72 women) aged between 18 and 68 years ($M = 47.00$; $SD = 9.15$), from the various provinces that make up the region of Andalusia (Spain). Moreover, all individuals served by FAISEM are diagnosed with a Severe Mental Disorder, and the gender distribution within the institution is also skewed toward a higher proportion of males. Therefore, the sample in this study is considered representative of the broader population of FAISEM users. Key demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants are presented in Table 1.

The study employed a non-probabilistic purposive sampling method, based on the participants' willingness to voluntarily collaborate. This approach was chosen due to the specific characteristics of the target population—individuals with Severe Mental Disorders (SMD)—and the inherent difficulties in accessing a representative sample in this context. Although this strategy limits the generalization of the results to the total population served by FAISEM, which includes 9350 individuals in Andalusia, the sample of 311 participants represents 3.32 % of this population, providing a solid basis for exploring key trends and relationships among variables. In this regard, the 311 participants account for 3.32 % of the total individuals attended by FAISEM in Andalusia and ensure adequate statistical power to detect moderate effect sizes ($r \approx .3$) in correlational or regression analyses, with a power level of $1 - \beta = .80$, which is the recommended threshold.

1.2. Medication use in the sample

All participants in the present study were under pharmacological treatment, as is standard among FAISEM users, who are diagnosed with severe mental disorders. The medication regimens were highly individualized and adjusted to the clinical profiles and comorbidities of each user. Treatments included a wide range of psychotropic medications such as antipsychotics (e.g., clozapine, risperidone, olanzapine, paliperidone, aripiprazole), benzodiazepines and other anxiolytics (e.g., lorazepam, lorazepam, lormetazepam, clonazepam, diazepam), antidepressants (e.g., citalopram, escitalopram, sertraline, paroxetine), mood stabilizers (e.g., valproic acid, carbamazepine, lamotrigine, lithium), and long-acting injectable antipsychotics (e.g., Trevicta, Xeplion, Risperdal Consta). Many participants were also prescribed adjuvant medications for managing side effects, somatic comorbidities, or general health (e.g., omeprazole, simvastatin, enalapril, metformin, folic acid). This wide range of medications reflects the complex clinical needs of this population and reinforces the importance of individualized, multidisciplinary approaches to care.

Table 1
Characteristics of the participants.

Variable	n	%
Total participants	311	100 %
Gender: Male	239	76.85 %
Gender: Female	72	23.15 %
Age (Mean \pm SD)	(47.00 \pm 9.15)	–
Educational level (primary or less)	189	60.8 %
Employment status: Unemployed	265	85.2 %

1.3. Instruments

To assess physical fitness, various tests from the PREFIT Battery (Ortega et al., 2021) were utilized, including.

- **Lower body muscular strength:** The standing long jump test was used to measure lower body muscular strength (Martínez López, 2003). This test involves jumping forward from a standing position with feet together behind a starting line, without separating the feet during the jump.
- **Cardiorespiratory capacity:** A predictive field test of VO₂max was conducted due to its ease of application, low cost, and ability to test multiple participants simultaneously. The most widely used test globally, the 20-m shuttle run test (20m-SRT; Olds et al., 2006), also known as the 20m shuttle run or beep test, was employed.

For body composition, assessments were conducted by appointment at the Andalusian Center for Sports Medicine, using a bioimpedance device to evaluate the following.

- **Body fat percentage:** The healthy general percentage of body fat for men should range from 6 % to 24 %, while for women, it is between 14 % and 31 % (Gallagher et al., 2000).
- **Lean body mass percentage:** Lean body mass typically accounts for 60 %–90 % of total body weight, in male at least 60 % and for women at least 50 % (Kyle et al., 2003)
- **Visceral fat:** To assess visceral fat levels, a measurement scale ranging from 1 to 59 is used. This scale is applied based on the results obtained from any measurement method. Healthy visceral fat values are considered those below 12 according to standard manufacturer guidelines for visceral fat assessment using BIA (Tanita Corporation, 2008), values ≤ 12 are considered within the healthy range (Fox et al., 2007)

Eating behaviors were assessed using the "Food Consumption Frequency Questionnaire" (FCFQ; Trinidad-Rodríguez et al., 2008), which consists of 45 items and examines the frequency of consumption (weekly or monthly) of specific food groups. These include industrially processed food groups such as sugary carbonated beverages, industrial baked goods, candies, ice cream, energy drinks, and commercial juices.

Weekly physical activity level: The current stage of physical activity level was evaluated using a single-item measure developed by Marcus and Owen (1992). Participants were categorized into one of five stages.

1. I am not currently exercising and have no intention of starting in the next 6 months (Precontemplation).
2. I am not currently exercising, but I am thinking about starting in the next 6 months (Contemplation).
3. I currently exercise occasionally, but not regularly (Preparation).
4. I currently exercise regularly, but I have only been doing so for the past 6 months (Action).
5. I currently exercise regularly and have been doing so for more than 6 months (Maintenance).

Exercise was defined as activities such as "walking, running, swimming, cycling, etc." Regular exercise was defined as engaging in physical activity three or more times per week for at least 20 min per session.

Regarding psychological variables, the following were assessed.

- **Mental well-being:** The unidimensional Warwick–Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale (WEMWBS) was used. The validated and adapted Spanish version by Castellví et al. (2014) was implemented. The scale comprises 14 items referring to feelings or thoughts the individual may have experienced in the last 14 days (2 weeks). Responses to each item were recorded using a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 to 5, where 1 means the statement never occurred

during this time and 5 means it always occurred. Higher scores on this scale indicate higher levels of mental well-being, while lower scores suggest a poorer perception of mental well-being.

- **Quality of life:** The WHOQOL-BREF Quality of Life Scale, developed by the World Health Organization (1998; 1999) and adapted to the Spanish context by Flores-Herrera et al. (2018), was used. This scale comprises 26 items: the first two questions are independent and assess the individual's general perception of quality of life and health, respectively, while the remaining 24 items evaluate four specific dimensions of quality of life: physical (items 3, 4, 10, 15, 16, 17, and 18), psychological (items 5, 6, 7, 11, 19, and 26), social (items 20, 21, and 22), and environmental (items 8, 9, 12, 13, 14, 23, 24, and 25). Each question is scored on a 1-to-5 scale; higher scores indicate better quality of life. Negative items (3, 4, and 26) are reverse-scored, and the total scores are converted to a 0-to-100 scale to allow comparisons among domains, as these contain an unequal number of items. The perception of quality of life and health in older adults was classified as poor when scores ranged from 0 to 2.99, acceptable from 3 to 3.99, and high from 4 to 5.

1.4. Procedure

Authorization and evaluation of the project were requested from the Bioethics Committee of the University of Almería. Once a positive report was obtained, users of the Andalusian Public Foundation for the Social Integration of People with Mental Illness (FAISEM) were informed about their participation in the project. The tests to be conducted, the characteristics and requirements for involvement, as well as the need to wear sportswear, comfortable clothing, and appropriate footwear on the days of the physical fitness tests, were thoroughly explained. Informed consent for participation was collected anonymously and voluntarily.

1.5. Data analysis

First, descriptive statistics of the sample, including age and gender, were analyzed. Subsequently, a bivariate correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationships between the study variables: body composition, physical fitness test results, weekly physical activity levels, eating habits, and perceptions of mental well-being and quality of life. Additionally, linear regression analyses were performed to evaluate the impact of time spent on physical activity and other related factors (such as cigarette consumption, consumption of ultra-processed foods, lean mass, body fat, and visceral fat) on mental well-being and quality of life. Two models were developed for each dependent variable: a simple model with time spent on physical activity as the sole predictor, and another model that included the additional predictors mentioned above. For data analysis and processing, the SPSS statistical software, version 29, was used.

2. Results

2.1. Descriptive statistics

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics for the different variables analyzed, disaggregated by gender. The analysis of body composition reveals significant health concerns in both men and women with SMD. Among men, body fat levels average 26.56 %, exceeding the general recommended threshold of 24 % for adult males. In the case of women, the average body fat percentage reaches 37.18 %, which also surpasses the healthy reference value of approximately 31 % for adult females (Gallagher et al., 2000). Lean mass is similarly deficient: male participants show a mean lean mass of 60.52 %, just at the minimum recommended level, while female participants fall well below the optimal range, with a mean of 47.42 % (Kyle et al., 2003). Visceral fat levels also show differences by gender; while male participants are, on average, slightly above the recommended upper limit ($M = 12.52$) (Fox et al.,

Table 2
Descriptive statistics and correlations between variables.

	Men		Women	
	M	SD	M	SD
1. Body fat	26.56 %	7.68	37.18 %	9.61
2. Lean mass	60.52 %	8.00	47.42 %	7.41
3. Visceral fat	12.52	5.65	9.55	4.62
4. Endurance	300.97	254.81	183.56	177.68
5. Long jump (m)	1.25	.43	.90	.43
6. Weekly PA level ^a	2.58	1.25		
7. Weekly UPP-C ^a	16.92	10.32		
8. Tobacco	9.97	11.63	7.27	9.61
9. Mental well-being ^a	3.48	.73		
10. Quality of life ^a	3.33	.51		

Note. UPP-C: Ultra-Processed Product Consumption.

^a Total sample results.

2007), female participants remain below the critical threshold ($M = 9.55$). These findings highlight widespread imbalances in body composition that may place individuals with SMD at increased risk for physical health complications, reinforcing the importance of targeted health promotion strategies for this population.

Regarding the results of the physical fitness evaluations, the indicators suggest an unfavorable physical condition among participants (Ortega et al., 2021). Specifically, cardiorespiratory endurance, expressed as estimated VO_2 max, averaged 30.10 ml/kg/min for men and 18.36 ml/kg/min for women. These values fall below the recommended thresholds for healthy adults of similar age, which are approximately 34 ml/kg/min for men and 27 ml/kg/min for women (American College of Sports Medicine, 2017; Shvartz and Reibold, 1990). Similarly, lower body strength, measured by the standing long jump, also showed suboptimal performance in both sexes. Men reached a mean distance of 1.25 m ($SD = .43$), while women averaged .90 m ($SD = .43$). These values fall short of the reference minimum of 1.80 m for men and 1.51 m for women, based on adult population norms (Ortega et al., 2021), and indicate insufficient muscular strength.

The physical activity level is moderate, with a scale ranging from 1 (indicating no activity) to 5 (indicating sustained regular practice for more than six months).

In terms of smoking, 65.59 % of the sample were classified as heavy smokers ($n = 204$), defined as individuals who smoke more than 10 cigarettes per day. Within this subgroup, the average daily consumption was 19 cigarettes/day. When considering the entire sample ($N = 311$), the mean daily consumption was 9.97 cigarettes ($SD = 11.63$) for men and 7.27 cigarettes ($SD = 9.61$) for women. These figures reflect both the high prevalence and the intensity of tobacco use in this population with severe mental disorders.

Regarding dietary and consumption habits, there is a notable excessive use of tobacco, with an average close to one pack per day. Similarly, the consumption of industrially processed products is reported as daily.

Table 3
Bivariate correlations between study variables.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1. Body fat	–	–.048	.516***	–.298***	–.301***	–.240***	.197**	.005	–.070	–.015
2. Lean mass		–	.191**	.143*	.167*	.178**	.033	.113	.011	.050
3. Visceral fat			–	–.299**	–.210**	–.425***	.201**	.109*	–.217**	–.136*
4. Endurance				–	.471***	.254***	–.102	–.073	.097	.044
5. Long jump (m)					–	.209**	–.079	–.014	.063	.001
6. Weekly PA level						–	–.196**	–.058	.380***	.320***
7. Weekly UPP-C							–	.008	.060	.090
8. Tobacco								–	–.032	–.017
9. Mental well-being									–	.816***
10. Quality of life										–

* $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$.

Note. UPP-C: Ultra-Processed Product Consumption.

When analyzing psychological variables, represented in this study by mental well-being and quality of life, values corresponding to normal ranges were observed, although there remains room for further improvement.

2.2. Correlation analysis

Table 3 presents the results of the Pearson correlation analysis, highlighting significant relationships among the various variables studied. Significant correlations are marked with an asterisk.

Regarding associations within the domain of body composition, notable correlations are observed between body fat and visceral fat, which exhibit a moderate degree of relationship. Moderate correlations are also found between body fat and performance in physical fitness tests, as well as with physical activity levels, although the latter is of low intensity. Additionally, muscle mass positively correlates with visceral fat at a moderate level. Visceral fat, in turn, shows a similar correlation, albeit of low intensity, with smoking habits and a negative correlation with performance in the physical tests conducted.

The variable linked to the endurance test exhibits a low-intensity correlation with physical activity levels, similar to the standing long jump test, which also shows a positive correlation. Meanwhile, physical activity levels demonstrate a positive, though low-magnitude, correlation with both quality of life and mental well-being. Mental well-being, in turn, reveals a significant positive correlation with quality of life.

2.3. Linear regression analysis

Linear regression analyses were conducted to evaluate the impact of physical activity and other related factors on mental well-being and quality of life in the studied population. The results are presented in Tables 4 and 5.

In Table 4, the general statistics of the fitted models for both dependent variables are summarized. For mental well-being, Model 1, which included time spent on physical activity (PA Time) as the sole predictor, explained 4.6 % of the variance ($R^2 = .046$) and was statistically significant ($F(1,176) = 8.538, p = .004$). When additional predictors were added in Model 2 (number of daily cigarettes, consumption of ultra-processed foods, muscle mass, body fat percentage, and visceral fat index), the increase in explained variance was minimal ($\Delta R^2 = .018$) and not significant ($F(5,171) = .661, p = .654$).

For quality of life, Model 1 explained 9.5 % of the variance ($R^2 = .095$) with a significant effect ($F(1,175) = 18.265, p < .001$). In Model 2, the explained variance increased slightly ($R^2 = .116$), but the change was not significant ($\Delta R^2 = .022, F(5,170) = .841, p = .523$).

Table 5 details the coefficients of the models for each dependent variable. In Model 1, time spent on physical activity was significantly associated with both mental well-being ($B = .078, p = .004$) and quality of life ($B = .115, p < .001$). In Model 2, time spent on physical activity maintained a significant relationship with both dependent variables (p

Table 4

Regression analysis results for the impact of physical activity and related factors on mental well-being and quality of life.

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Standar error of estimate	ΔR2	ΔF	df1	df2	p(ΔF)
Mental well-being									
1	.215	.046	.041	.72068	.046	8.538	1	176	.004
2	.254	.064	.032	.72417	.018	.661	5	171	.654
Quality of life									
1	.307	.095	.089	.50952	.095	18.265	1	175	.000
2	.341	.116	.085	.51068	.022	.841	5	170	.523

Note: Model 1 includes only “Time spent on physical activity” as the predictor. Model 2 includes the following predictors: Time spent on physical activity, number of cigarettes, ultra-processed food consumption, muscle mass, body fat percentage, and visceral fat index.

Table 5

Regression coefficients for mental well-being and quality of life.

Predictor	Dependent variable	B	Std. error	Beta	t	p	λ	VIF
Model 1								
(Constant)	Mental well-being	2.940	.108	–	27.184	.000	–	–
PA time	Mental well-being	.078	.027	.215	2.921	.004	1.000	1.000
(Constant)	Quality of life	2.981	.103	–	28.833	.000	–	–
PA time	Quality of life	.115	.027	.307	4.274	.000	1.000	1.000
Model 2								
(Constant)	Mental well-being	3.025	.317	–	9.540	.000	–	–
PA time	Mental well-being	.074	.032	.204	2.321	.022	.706	1.416
UPP-C	Mental well-being	.005	.005	.086	1.026	.306	.918	1.089
Number of cigarettes	Mental well-being	–.001	.005	–.015	–.181	.857	.952	1.051
Fat %	Mental well-being	.006	.007	.094	.896	.371	.564	1.775
Muscle mass	Mental well-being	–.003	.006	–.046	–.481	.631	.729	1.372
Visceral fat	Mental well-being	–.009	.011	–.108	–.847	.398	.463	2.161
(Constant)	Quality of life	3.043	.310	–	9.813	.000	–	–
PA time	Quality of life	.112	.032	.300	3.499	.001	.706	1.416
UPP-C	Quality of life	.004	.004	.072	.959	.339	.918	1.089
Number of cigarettes	Quality of life	–.001	.004	–.017	–.231	.818	.952	1.051
Fat %	Quality of life	.005	.006	.078	.816	.416	.564	1.775
Muscle mass	Quality of life	–.002	.005	–.033	–.389	.698	.729	1.372
Visceral fat	Quality of life	–.012	.009	–.146	–1.373	.172	.463	2.161

Note: λ = Tolerance.

= .022 and p = .001, respectively), while the other predictors did not reach statistical significance, except for visceral fat, which showed a non-significant negative trend with quality of life (B = –.012, p = .172).

These results indicate a consistent relationship between time spent on physical activity and indicators of mental well-being and quality of life. However, the multivariable model does not significantly improve the explained variance, emphasizing the primary role of physical activity in these outcomes.

3. Discussion

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the physical, dietary, and psychological conditions in individuals with severe mental disorders (SMD). The results reveal a concerning situation across multiple dimensions, including body composition, dietary habits, physical activity levels, and variables related to quality of life and well-being, such as mental well-being and quality of life itself. Based on these findings, the study explores the implications and potential intervention strategies, taking into account methodological limitations and the connections between the variables analyzed.

3.1. Physical conditions and body composition

The population with SMD exhibits significant deficiencies in body composition. The high levels of body fat and visceral fat found in this study align with previous research highlighting the high prevalence of obesity and metabolic issues in this population (Correll et al., 2017; Vancampfort et al., 2015). These alterations not only increase the risk of cardiovascular diseases and metabolic syndrome but are also linked to

reduced quality of life and life expectancy (Lawrence et al., 2013).

Visceral fat accumulation is particularly concerning, as it is associated with cardiometabolic risk factors such as insulin resistance and systemic inflammation (Haberka et al., 2018; Janochova et al., 2019). Although the average visceral fat values in this study are near the healthy threshold, any additional increase could trigger significant complications. This underscores the need for early interventions targeting both dietary factors and physical activity levels.

In contrast, the participants’ lean mass falls below healthy standards, reflecting a deterioration in muscle tissue and physical functionality (Vancampfort et al., 2016). This condition could lead to issues such as sarcopenia, reduced muscular strength, and a higher risk of falls—critical factors for independence and quality of life in this population (Pérez-Cruzado et al., 2018).

3.2. Dietary habits and consumption of ultra-processed products

The results reveal a dietary pattern characterized by low consumption of fresh foods and high intake of ultra-processed products. This finding aligns with previous studies indicating that individuals with SMD tend to consume large quantities of refined carbohydrates, saturated fats, and sugar-rich foods, while their intake of fruits, vegetables, and essential nutrients is insufficient (Aucoin et al., 2018; Teasdale et al., 2019). This dietary imbalance not only contributes to the accumulation of visceral fat but also negatively impacts psychological well-being, as nutrient-poor diets have been linked to increased symptoms of anxiety and depression (Monteiro et al., 2017; Lawrence and Baker, 2019).

Moreover, the excessive consumption of ultra-processed products

highlights the importance of considering not only dietary preferences but also the structural barriers faced by individuals with SMD. These barriers include limited access to healthy foods, the high cost of such products, and a lack of nutritional knowledge (Martland et al., 2021). Interventions aimed at reducing the consumption of ultra-processed foods and promoting balanced diets should be tailored to the specific needs of this population, taking into account factors such as economic accessibility and social support.

3.3. Tobacco consumption

The high prevalence of tobacco use observed in this study (65.59 % classified as heavy smokers) highlights a critical area of concern in the health profile of individuals with SMD. These rates are substantially higher than those reported in the general population and consistent with previous research on smoking in psychiatric populations (De Leon and Diaz, 2005; Prochaska et al., 2017). The average daily consumption—close to one pack per day among smokers—reflects both the intensity of use and the potential health burden. Tobacco use has been associated with increased visceral fat, metabolic dysregulation, and reduced effectiveness of psychotropic medication (Anthamatten and Henry-Okafor, 2025). Moreover, it negatively impacts mental health by reinforcing addiction cycles and impairing self-regulation and motivation. Integrated intervention strategies should address tobacco cessation as a core component of health promotion for this population.

3.4. Physical activity and sedentary behavior

The level of physical activity observed among participants is insufficient to meet the minimum recommendations of the World Health Organization (WHO, 2020). This finding aligns with research documenting high levels of sedentary behavior in individuals with SMD, largely attributed to the side effects of antipsychotic medications and a barriers to motivation (Ashdown-Franks et al., 2018; Stubbs et al., 2018).

Sedentary behavior has negative consequences on both physical and psychological levels. Physically, it is associated with a decline in cardiorespiratory capacity and muscle strength (Pérez-Cruzado et al., 2018). Psychologically, it limits individuals' ability to engage in social activities, exacerbating isolation and reducing mental well-being (Berghöfer et al., 2020). This study demonstrates a significant correlation between physical activity levels and variables such as mental well-being and quality of life, supporting the importance of promoting physical activity as part of an integrated intervention strategy.

Time dedicated to physical activity showed a positive correlation with both mental well-being and quality of life, consistent with previous studies highlighting its role as a protective factor against the negative effects of sedentary behavior in this population (Stubbs et al., 2018; Ashdown-Franks et al., 2018). In both regression analyses, physical activity was the only significant predictor in the simpler models, explaining 4.6 % of the variance in mental well-being and 9.5 % in quality of life. However, the inclusion of additional predictors (such as cigarette consumption, ultra-processed food intake, visceral fat, and muscle mass) did not significantly improve the explained variance in psychological variables. This suggests that the impact of physical activity on these dimensions may be more direct and less mediated by other physiological or dietary variables.

Nonetheless, given the use of self-reported measures, a potential bias due to social desirability cannot be ruled out, which may have led participants to overestimate their actual levels of physical activity. These findings underscore the importance of promoting programs to increase regular physical activity in individuals with SMD.

Achieving adherence to physical activity programs remains a challenge. Previous studies have identified barriers to interest and engagement included social stigma, limited resources, and restricted Access to adapted programs (Méndez-Aguado et al., 2023; Romain et al., 2020).

Therefore, interventions must be highly personalized, employing a gradual and flexible approach that considers these barriers and promotes long-term adherence.

3.5. Mental well-being and quality of life

In the psychological domain, study participants exhibited low levels of mental well-being and quality of life, though within acceptable ranges compared to other studies on SMD (Berghöfer et al., 2020; Vaca and Martínez, 2019). These findings reflect the complex interplay of social, physical, and emotional factors that affect this population. Notably, mental well-being and quality of life observed in this study, while sub-optimal, appear to be less severely impacted than those reported in other studies involving individuals with SMD (Vancampfort et al., 2015; Stubbs et al., 2018). Several factors may explain this relative preservation. First, the participants were recruited through FAISEM, an institution that provides stable, community-based psychosocial support, which has been shown to buffer psychological distress and promote social integration (Laviana, 2012). La atención a las personas con esquizofrenia y otros trastornos mentales graves desde los servicios públicos: una atención integral e integrada en un modelo comunitario. Apuntes de Psicología, 459–476.). This structural support may have contributed positively to participants' perceived well-being. Second, methodological differences—such as the instruments used, cultural context, or the timing of assessment—may also explain the discrepancy. Finally, the voluntary nature of participation may have introduced a selection bias toward individuals with relatively better functioning or higher engagement with support services.

Although not directly assessed in this study, social and self-stigma have been widely identified in the literature as important psychological challenges affecting individuals with SMD (Nevarez-Flores et al., 2019). These forms of stigma can limit access to healthcare, employment, and social integration, indirectly influencing quality of life and psychological well-being. Future research should explore how stigma may interact with lifestyle variables such as diet, physical activity, and tobacco use, in order to develop more comprehensive intervention strategies. Additionally, medication side effects, such as weight gain and drowsiness, are also known to impair self-esteem and overall well-being (Lien et al., 2018; Rezaie et al., 2017).

Physical activity, although limited in this population, has been shown to be an effective tool for improving psychological well-being. Numerous studies have documented that regular participation in physical activities reduces anxiety and depression, enhances mood, and increases self-esteem (Stubbs et al., 2018; Giroir and Wright, 2018). This effect is evident in the findings of the present study, where physical activity levels positively correlate with both mental well-being and quality of life.

3.6. Interaction between the variables studied

One of the main strengths of this study is its focus on the interactions between physical, dietary, and psychological variables. For instance, physical activity levels serve as a bridge between body composition and psychological variables. Increased physical activity reduces visceral fat and improves lean mass, which, in turn, contributes to better quality of life and mental well-being (Méndez-Aguado et al., 2023; Martín-Rodríguez et al., 2024).

Additionally, the consumption of ultra-processed products and smoking have a direct impact on both physical and psychological variables. For example, smoking is associated with increased visceral fat, while a diet high in ultra-processed foods negatively affects both body composition and mental well-being (Monteiro et al., 2017; Ortega et al., 2021). These interactions highlight the need for a multidimensional approach to interventions, addressing physical, dietary, and psychological aspects simultaneously.

4. Study limitations

Despite its contributions, this study has certain limitations. The sample selection was not completely random, which could limit the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, the use of self-reported questionnaires may have introduced biases, particularly in variables such as food consumption and physical activity, where participants might have overestimated or underestimated their behaviors (Trinidad-Rodríguez et al., 2008). In particular, a potential bias due to social desirability cannot be ruled out, especially considering the stigma frequently associated with unhealthy behaviors in individuals with severe mental disorders. This may have led participants to report behaviors more socially acceptable than those actually performed.

Another limitation is the absence of disaggregated clinical data regarding specific treatment modalities. Although all participants were under pharmacological treatment—as is standard among FAISEM users—the wide variability in medications, dosages, and frequency, which are individually tailored by different medical teams across provinces, made it unfeasible to conduct a detailed quantitative analysis of treatment variables. Instead, we opted to provide a qualitative description of the pharmacological regimens, reflecting the complexity and individualization of care in this population. Similarly, although diagnostic data were collected, a portion of participants declined to report their specific diagnoses. As a result, we based our classification on the known clinical profile of FAISEM users, all of whom meet the criteria for Severe Mental Disorder.

Additionally, the cross-sectional nature of the study limits the possibility of establishing causal relationships between variables. While significant correlations were identified, it is not possible to determine, for example, whether low physical activity levels cause poorer quality of life or if the latter reduces motivation to engage in physical activity. Future longitudinal research could address these limitations and provide a clearer understanding of causal relationships.

5. Implications and future recommendations

The findings of this study have important implications for the design of interventions aimed at improving the quality of life and well-being of individuals with SMD. First, it is essential to promote tailored physical activity programs that consider the specific barriers faced by this population and provide a gradual and accessible approach. Second, educational and supportive strategies are needed to improve dietary habits by reducing the consumption of ultra-processed foods and promoting balanced diets. Third, interventions should address social stigma and self-stigma, fostering a more inclusive environment that facilitates access to healthcare services and social opportunities.

In conclusion, this study highlights the interconnectedness of physical, dietary, and psychological variables in individuals with SMD, emphasizing the importance of an integrated approach to improving their quality of life. Future research should explore these relationships longitudinally, include objective measurements of lifestyle behaviors (e. g., accelerometers for physical activity), and evaluate the effectiveness of comprehensive interventions, contributing to the development of more effective and equitable strategies.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

María Jesús Lirola: Writing – original draft, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Adolfo J. Cangas:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition. **Juan Leandro Cerezuola:** Project administration, Investigation. **Andrés López-Pardo:** Visualization, Resources, Project administration.

Data availability statement

Data presented in this study are available on reasonable request from the first author.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT to assist with the translation into English. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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